

Examining Inclusive Education Practices for Children with Disabilities in the United Arab Emirates

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 24, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: August 25, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Inclusive Education, Children With Disabilities, Attitudes</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8280213</p>	<p><i>This study examines inclusive education practices for children with disabilities in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) by examining teachers' attitudes toward inclusion. The study sample consisted of 310 mainstream and special-education teachers from all of the UAE Emirates. Statistical analyses were used to examine the relationships between predictors. The findings showed that all of the adult target groups demonstrated positive attitudes towards educational inclusion. Female teachers had more positive attitudes towards inclusion than male teachers. The study results also found that special-education teachers had more positive attitudes than regular teachers. There was a link between the knowledge, skills, and attitudes towards inclusion of regular and special-education teachers; all teachers with knowledge, skills, and training in the area of special education received high scores for positive attitudes towards inclusion.</i></p>

Introduction

Educational inclusion is a reform process designed to promote diversity among students in general-education classrooms. Students are grouped in classrooms with no regard for their ethnic or religious backgrounds, social status, gender, or abilities (Alzyoudi, Al Saratwai, & Dooden, 2011; Ainscow, & Miles, 2008). Educational inclusion has become a "global agenda," with international organizations and governments committing themselves to the inclusive development of education, at least in their public pronouncements (Mitchell, 2005). Developing teaching methods that take into consideration the academic learning and social integration of all students is a major task in inclusive settings. This signifies a change in attitudes towards diversity and a reduction in discrimination (WHO, 2011).

Research has shown that teachers have direct responsibility for implementing inclusion in the classroom context; their commitment and motivation are essential for effecting the necessary changes and producing more positive outcomes through inclusive education. Studies have particularly focused on the importance of teachers' attitudes and the relationship between positive attitudes and the successful implementation of inclusive education practices (Al Zyoudi et al., 2011; Boer, Pijl, & Minnaert, 2011; Khochen, & Radford, 2012; Loreman, 2014; Sandhu, 2017). According to Wolstenholme (2010), positive attitudes among teachers are a key factor in effective inclusive, while negative attitudes are a barrier to inclusion.

Many countries of the world have laws that mandate the inclusion of students with disabilities in regular classrooms. In the UAE, the practice of inclusive education has so far been largely determined by the Ministry of Education and ADEC. In 2006, UAE Federal Law No. 29, "Concerning the Rights of People with Special Needs," guaranteed (in Mandate number 12) equal educational opportunities for people with special needs at all institutes of general education, vocational training, adult education, and continuing education, by offering mainstream and special-education curricula in sign language, Braille, and other appropriate formats. Furthermore, the UAE have formally expressed their support for the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) for the implementation of inclusion policies. The United Nations Education, Science, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) continues to push for inclusionary practices in more countries, with the publication of *The Right to Education for Persons with Disabilities: Towards Inclusion*.

Researchers have carried out many studies worldwide to assess teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education, setting aside academic specialties and student levels. In the United States, teachers disapproved of negative attitudes toward inclusive education (Cook, Cameron, & Tankersley, 2007; DeBettencourt, 1999; Everington, Steven, & Winters, 1999; Hammond, & Lawrence, 2003; Rheams, & Bain, 2005; Wilkins, & Nietfeld, 2004). Avramidis and Kalyva (2007) assessed teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education in Greece, finding that teachers had positive attitudes toward inclusion. By contrast, Batsiou et al.'s 2008 study found that 179 Greek and Cypriot teachers had negative attitudes toward inclusive education. In the United Kingdom, Sadler (2005) found that teachers had limited knowledge of and negative attitudes toward inclusive education. Ghanizadeh et al. (2006) assessed teacher attitudes toward inclusive education in Iran, reporting that

35 participants (78% of their sample) had negative attitudes toward inclusive programs; these participants preferred separate classes for students with special needs. In Zimbabwe, most teachers opposed inclusive education; they too preferred separate classes for children with special needs (Mushoriwa, 2001). By contrast, studies carried out in India and Portugal found that teachers had positive attitudes toward inclusion (Freire & César, 2003; Parasuram, 2006).

An assessment of the views of 224 teachers in China on inclusive education found that both students and teachers had a negative view of inclusivity because they felt the school curriculum was too difficult for disabled students (Pearson et al., 2003). In Korea, teachers favored inclusive education if schools and class settings were available (Kim, Park, & Snell, 2005); studies conducted in New Zealand and Turkey obtained similar results (Monsen & Frederickson, 2004; Sari, 2007). Anwar and Sulman's 2012 study showed that most general school educators were more positive about physically disabled students participating in inclusive programs than about cognitively disabled students.

Apart from a few studies addressing teachers' attitudes towards inclusion (e.g., Alzyoudi et al., 2011; Gaad, 2004), no detailed empirical studies have explored the attitudes of UAE teachers towards inclusive practices for children with special educational needs. Research has shown that, for students with special educational needs, teaching is a very important determining factor in the successful implementation of inclusive education (Bargerhuff, 2013, Florin, Earle, Loremann, & Sharma, 2011, Hannu, Petra, Mima, & Olli-Pekka, 2012). Several studies have reported that mainstream-classroom teachers are not supportive of educational inclusion (i.e. Minke, Bear, Deemer, & Griffin, 1996; Reiter, Tirosh, 1998). Others (i.e. Villa, Thousand, Meyers, & Navin, 1996; Ward, Center, & Bochner, 1994) have found that mainstream-classroom teachers have relatively favorable attitudes. A study comparing regular and special-education teachers found that special-education teachers were more accepting of inclusion than mainstream-classroom teachers (Taylor et al., 1997; Balboni, & Pedrabissi, 2000; Wei, & Yuen, 2000; Chen, 2006; Fakolade, & Adeniyi, 2009). In a study conducted by Zoniou-Sideri and Vlachou (2006) on Greek teachers' beliefs about educational inclusion, mainstream teachers were found to hold a number of restrictive and conflicting beliefs about disability and educational inclusion. Although they stated that educational inclusion was needed to improve the way ordinary schools functioned and to reduce the marginalization and stigmatization of students with disabilities, they also saw segregated special education as important because it offered disabled students a secure and protective environment while addressing some of the deficiencies of mainstream education.

The relationship between attitudes toward inclusion and demographic information is inconsistent in relation to gender. Some studies have found gender differences in teacher's attitudes towards inclusion (e.g., Avramidis and Kalyva, 2007; Srivastava et al., 2015; Gaad et al., 2004). However, Almotairi's 2013 research on the attitudes of teachers in Kuwait found definite gender differences. Although teachers of both genders were strong proponents of inclusion, male teachers were generally more positive than female teachers about teaching students with special educational needs in mainstream classrooms. Similar results were reported by Qaraqish (2008), who found that the attitudes of Saudi female teachers were more negative than those of male teachers when it came to educational inclusion for students with behavioral problems. However, other studies (e.g., Ellins, 2004; Gyimah, 2006; Wan, & Huang, 2005) found no difference in the attitudes of male and female teachers.

Many educational experts and educational organizations have gone to great lengths to identify competencies and to develop training programs to prepare both mainstream and special-education teachers to implement educational inclusion (Sebba & Ainsco, 1996; York & Reynolds, 1996; Council for Exceptional Children, 2001). The self-efficacy of teachers generates the behavior and motivation needed to succeed in teacher education (Pajares, 1992). In Social Learning Theory, Bandura (1977, 1986) emphasizes the importance of self-efficacy. Some researchers (i.e., Gibson & Dembo, 1984; Dembo & Gibson, 1985) applied the construct of self-efficacy to teaching, developing a way of measuring teacher efficacy that yielded a two-factor structure. The first factor was the teacher's sense of overall teaching efficacy, which related to his or her ability to bring about desired outcomes. The second factor was the teacher's sense of personal teaching efficacy, which reflected the belief that he or she had the necessary skills and abilities to influence student learning and behavior. Teachers with higher levels of self-efficacy are less critical of student errors, have the ability to work longer with struggling students, and are more willing to try new teaching methods to meet the needs of their students. Teachers with a greater sense of efficacy have been found by some researchers (i.e. Soodaket et al., 1998) to be less likely to refer students with learning and behavior problems to special education. A lack of a belief in their own knowledge and skills among teachers is therefore considered a major obstacle to their willingness to teach students with disabilities in inclusive classrooms. Many experts in the field of inclusive education support this point of view. Several cautionary reports have suggested that special (Fisher et al., 2003; Kilgore & Griffin, 1998) and mainstream (Davern, 1999; Lesar, Penner, Habel, & Coleman, 1997; Schumm & Vaughn, 1991) educators may not have the necessary professional skills to successfully instruct students in diverse, inclusive classrooms. Furthermore, mainstream school teachers have themselves reported that they do not have the necessary skills to teach students with disabilities (Cook, 2001; Rose, 2001). In his 2006 study, Abbott showed

that most U.S. head teachers believed that basic teacher education did not fully prepare students for inclusive classrooms, as the teaching methods used to teach students with disabilities in inclusive classrooms also needed to be inclusive. Schools will not become inclusive by transplanting special-education thinking and practice. As Ainscow (1999) has suggested, in setting up inclusive classrooms, schools must move from planning for individualized teaching toward a perspective that seeks to personalize learning by engaging with the whole class. If this principle is kept in mind, many ideas about effective teaching become relevant; "what is particular to an inclusive pedagogy is the way teachers conceptualize notion of difference" (Ainscow & Miles, 2008, p.9).

Although professional development for in-service teachers remains a prominent approach to preparing for educational inclusion, an increased emphasis has been placed on the role and responsibilities of teacher-preparation programs, which prepare new educators to teach in inclusive classrooms. According to Al Zyoudi et al. (2011) and Forlin (2004), universities and colleges of education should play a significant role in preparing pre-service teachers to address their own concerns and beliefs about educating disabled students in inclusive settings. These teachers should increase their knowledge of disabilities and strive to understand students who are marginalized as a result of cultural, religious, ethnic, socio-economic, or psychological factors. It is even more important to equip teachers to work in more diverse classrooms from the start of their teaching careers (Meijer, 2010). The move towards inclusive schooling requires schools to address professional development with regard to schools and teachers. Schools should enhance the skills and knowledge of teachers to address the learning needs of all students. Training, access to information, and support must all be sustained, as staff development is most powerful when it is conducted for long enough and often enough to assure progressive gains in confidence, knowledge and skills (Dennis & Launcelot, 2011). Teachers should be provided with guidelines for planning appropriate curricula to successfully incorporate students with disabilities into mainstream classrooms (Forlin, 2003; Forlin et al., 2001).

The present study poses the following questions:

1. What are the attitudes of mainstream and special-education teachers towards inclusion?
2. Do the stakeholders' gender and type (e.g., mainstream or special-education teachers) affect their attitudes towards inclusion?
3. How do special-education teachers perceive their own knowledge and skills, in relation to teaching students with disabilities in inclusive classrooms?

Methods

Sample

To select an appropriate sample, the research investigators arranged for all government schools in the UAE (n=451) to be visited, so that data could be collected from target groups. All mainstream-classroom teachers and special-education teachers in these schools were invited to participate in the study. Of this group, 310 teachers agreed to complete the scales and questionnaires. Table 1 shows the number of male and female students (N=310) who participated in the study, indicating their school grade and the Emirates they lived in.

Instruments

The following seven instruments were developed to collect data for this project; the process of developing each instrument is explained below.

The researchers developed this scale to gather data from target groups, as a way of investigating teachers' attitudes towards including students with disabilities in mainstream schools in the UAE. The target group included special-education and mainstream-classroom teachers. This scale was developed to measure three attitudinal components: behavioral, emotional, and cognitive attitudes. Initially, the researchers developed 64 items; after a review, the number was reduced to 45. These items were then further reviewed by experts in the field and reduced to 34 items. After conducting a factor analysis of the items, a final group of 19 items was selected. Test-retest reliability for the scale was ascertained using a sample of 307 participants from the target groups; the reliability coefficient was 0.87. The internal consistency of the scale was also studied using a sample of 587 people; Cronbach's Alpha was 0.96.

Mainstream-classroom Teachers' Scale

This scale was developed to measure the efficacy of mainstream schoolteachers in teaching children with disabilities in the ordinary UAE school system. This scale measures many special education-related skills that mainstream teachers may have mastered. Initially, the researchers developed 40 items, which they reduced to 39; a further review by experts winnowed the list to 29 items. After a factor analysis, a final group of 23 items was selected. The test-retest reliability of the scale was examined using a sample of 100 mainstream schoolteachers; the reliability coefficient was 0.92. The internal consistency of the scale was studied using a sample of 460 mainstream schoolteachers; the Cronbach's Alpha was 0.93.

The Special-education Teachers' Scale

This scale was developed to measure the efficacy of special-education teachers teaching students with disabilities or educational challenges in mainstream schools in the UAE. This scale measures many special education-related skills that special-education teachers may have mastered. Initially the researchers developed

52 items, which they reduced to 49; a further review by experts winnowed the list to 44 items. After a factor analysis, a final group of 42 items was selected. The test-retest reliability of the scale was examined using a sample of 50 special-education teachers and the reliability coefficient was 0.95. The internal consistency of the scale studied using a sample of 252 special-education teachers; the Cronbach's Alpha was 0.97.

Table 1 (below) shows the internal consistency and test-retest reliability of these scales.

Scales	No. of Items	Internal Consistency		Test-retest Reliability	
		a-Coefficient	N	r	N
Mainstream Classroom Teachers' Scale	23	0.93	460	.92	100
Special Education Teachers' Scale	42	0.97	252	0.95	50

RESULTS

The present study has examined inclusive education practices for children with disabilities in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) by examining attitudes towards inclusion. In addition, it has assessed the extent to which teachers have the skills and knowledge they need to implement best practices in meeting the learning needs of students with disabilities. It has also investigated the accessibility of school environments for students with disabilities.

Each research question and the relevant findings are presented below.

Research Question 1: What are the attitudes of regular and special-education teachers towards inclusion?

This study investigated the attitudes of adult target groups towards including students with disabilities in mainstream schools. The participants responded to 19 attitude statements using a three-point Likert-type scale: the possible responses were "strongly agree," "agree," and "do not agree." Participant scores could therefore range between 19 (very negative attitudes) and 57 (very positive attitudes), with a theoretical mean of 38. The higher the score, the more positive the participant's attitudes. Descriptive statistics were calculated using means and standard deviations. The results revealed that the target groups displayed positive attitudes towards including students with disabilities in mainstream schools; almost all target groups had mean scores that were higher than the theoretical mean for the scale. When the three highest means were used to compare attitudes toward educational inclusion among the target groups, special-education teachers had the most positive attitudes ($M=44.50$; $SD=9.02$), followed by mainstream teachers ($M=40.24$; $SD=9.03$).

This finding suggests that special-education teachers have a more positive attitude toward students with disabilities and toward adapting teaching toward various disabilities than their colleagues in mainstream education; this finding confirms Fakolade and Adeniyi (2009). It may reflect the fact that teachers who are qualified to work with students with disabilities are able to change their teaching practices to accommodate such students. Mainstream teachers may have had limited or no training in inclusive teaching. As a result, such teachers may have to adapt, not only to a new group of students requiring additional support and alternative teaching strategies, but also to an inclusive school, which may differ from the type of school they envisioned themselves working in.

A lack of confidence about teaching students with disabilities was associated with negative attitudes toward inclusion. Thus, teachers' attitudes may be associated with their struggle to identify solutions to problems, such as the need to accommodate students with severe disabilities, or the lack of skills needed to deal with disabled students.

Research Question 2: Do the gender and type of stakeholders (mainstream-classroom teachers or special-education teachers) affect their attitudes towards inclusion?

The main effect of gender on target-group attitudes towards inclusion was investigated using two factors (2 adult roles) X (2 adult genders). An analysis of variance was carried out to examine this main effect. The results revealed that most female target groups demonstrated more positive attitudes towards educational inclusion than male target groups. The most positive attitudes were shown by female special-education teachers ($M=47.04$; $SD=8.24$), followed by mainstream male teachers ($M=42.31$; $SD=8.07$). The results of the current study add to the evidence that gender is a predictor of teachers' attitudes towards inclusion—and that male teachers tend to have a more negative attitude than female teachers. This result could reflect the fact that female teachers tend to use more sensitive, positive, and culturally appropriate terms and references than male teachers. This result has been supported by Avramidis and Kalyva (2007), Srivastava et al. (2015), and Gaad (2004). By

contrast, Almotairi (2013) and Qaraqish (2008) found that female teachers had more negative attitudes than male teachers towards educational inclusion for students with behavioral problems.

Research Question 3: How do special-education teachers perceive their own knowledge and skills when teaching students with disabilities in an inclusive classroom?

This research studied how special-education teachers perceived their own knowledge and skills when teaching students with disabilities in inclusive classrooms. The special-education teachers responded to 42 teaching knowledge and skill statements, using a three-point Likert-type scale, where the possible responses were “know it perfectly,” “somewhat know it,” and “don’t know it at all.” The teachers’ responses were analyzed using frequencies, as shown in Table 8, below. As the frequency table shows, many special-education teachers were confident that they perfectly understood many skills and aspects of knowledge; they did not understand a few others. The top five perfectly known skills and aspects of knowledge cited by the top 5% of special-education teachers were as follows: “an awareness of and a commitment to what the teaching profession requires” (86.7%); “the ability to manage a classroom” (86%); the “ability to meet individual differences among students in the classroom” (83.6%); “controlling the classroom environment” (83.5%); and “organizing the classroom environment” (83.2%).

On the other hand, the results also revealed that special-education teachers lacked a few teaching skills and aspects of knowledge. The five main skills not known by the top 5% of special-education teachers were as follows: “implementing and analyzing criterion-referenced test results” (23%); “implementing and analyzing norm-referenced test results” (20.8%); “differentiating instruction” (18.8%); “interpreting the results of formal and informal tests” (14.3%); and “methods of making curriculum-based measurements” (12.2%).

Other skills and aspects of teaching knowledge were only partially known. In this category, the five main areas were: “implementing and analyzing the results of criterion-referenced tests” (57.1%); “interpreting the results of formal and informal assessment tests” (55.7%); “implementing and analyzing the results of norm-referenced tests” (55.3%); “diagnosing criteria for each disability” (50.3%); and “the nature of services provided to students with disabilities, ranked from the least to the most restrictive environment” (47.5%). For more information on the special-education teachers’ perceived mastery of skills, in relation to teaching individuals with disabilities, see Table 2 below:

Table 2: Special education teachers’ perception of their own teaching knowledge and skills

Knowledge & Skill Statements	Perceived Mastery Level					
	Don't Know all(1)		Somewhat At Know (2)		Know It Perfectly (3)	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
1. Philosophy, principles, & objectives of special education	3	1.0	58	20.2	226	78.7
2. Nature of services provided to students with disabilities, ranked from the least to the most restrictive environment	15	5.4	132	47.5	131	47.1
3. Laws, regulations, & policies related to special education	12	4.2	124	43.4	150	52.4
4. Procedures for obtaining special education services	10	3.5	103	35.9	174	60.6
5. Procedures for developing an Individual Education Plan	7	2.5	57	20.3	217	77.2
6. Steps & procedures for referring students and identifying their eligibility for special education	9	3.1	81	28.3	196	68.5
7. Writing Individual Education Plan (IEP) reports	8	2.8	60	21.1	217	76.1
8. Procedures & policies for reassessing students with disabilities	23	8.1	119	41.9	284	50.0
9. Philosophy of teaching students with disabilities alongside non-disabled peers in the same classroom	22	7.7	121	42.3	143	50.0
10. Characteristics of students with disabilities	10	3.5	93	32.4	184	64.1
11. Criteria for diagnosing each disability	31	10.8	144	50.3	111	38.8
12. Criteria for obtaining special education services	26	9.1	127	44.6	132	46.3
13. Methods of gathering & analyzing data to develop an IEP	19	6.6	98	34.1	170	59.2
14. Using data to decide on a student's placement	18	6.3	112	39.2	156	54.5
15. Implementing & analyzing the results of norm-referenced tests.	59	20.8	157	56.3	68	23.9
16. Implementing & analyzing the results of criterion-referenced tests	66	23.0	164	57.1	57	19.9

17. Curriculum-based measurement methods	35	12.2	141	49.1	111	38.7
18. Using informal assessment tests, such as task analyses, observation, and interviews	20	7.0	129	44.9	138	48.1
19. Interpreting the results of formal& informal assessment tests	41	14.3	160	55.7	86	30.0
20. Selecting curricular content to meet students' individual needs	11	3.9	109	38.2	165	57.9
21. Modifying curricular content to meet students' individual needs	13	4.5	108	37.8	165	57.7
22. Developing new curricular learning units	34	12.0	128	45.2	121	42.8
23. Identifying the expected curriculum& how to teach it	20	7.0	119	41.5	148	51.6
24. Using differentiated instruction	54	18.8	125	43.6	108	37.6
25. Developing classroom activities to meet students' individual needs	4	1.4	92	32.3	189	66.3
26. Meeting students' individual needs in the classroom	2	0.7	45	15.7	239	83.6
27. Having the ability to manage classrooms	2	0.7	38	13.3	246	86.0
28. Planning& developing weekly and daily education programs as well as teaching sessions	8	2.8	74	25.9	204	71.3
29. Designing learning units to meet the individual needs of students	12	4.2	90	31.7	182	64.1
30. Organizing the classroom environment	1	0.3	47	16.4	238	83.2
31. Controlling the classroom environment	1	0.4	46	16.1	238	83.5
32. Identifying a student's unique skills	1	0.4	64	22.5	219	77.1
33. Identifying students' current levels in various academic areas.	2	0.7	54	18.9	229	80.4
34. Using a co-operative teaching strategy	2	0.7	56	19.6	228	79.7
35. Coordinating with other professionals involved in student problems	10	3.5	85	29.8	190	66.7
36. Working with other professionals when the need arises	10	3.5	90	31.6	185	64.9
37. Dealing with the needs of families of children with disabilities	12	4.2	84	29.3	191	66.6
38. Communicating& working with the families of students with disabilities	5	1.7	69	24.1	212	74.1
39. Managing students' behavior& social interactions	6	2.1	93	32.5	187	65.4
40. Supervising assistant teachers	21	7.3	102	35.7	163	57.0
41. Training assistant teachers	28	9.8	124	43.4	134	46.9
42. Using various instructional strategies	11	3.9	80	27.9	196	68.3

Knowledge appears to be a key factor that influences teachers' ability to change their teaching practices. Teachers' knowledge can be divided into content knowledge (knowledge about the subject), pedagogical knowledge (including teaching and classroom management strategies), and pedagogical content knowledge (how to teach particular content to a specific student in a defined context). Having been trained to teach students with disabilities was associated with positive attitudes towards inclusion. However, upholding a degree in inclusive teaching did not contribute to the model. Future research could examine the extent to which training specifically designed to prepare teachers to work with disabled students is better at incorporating all aspects of knowledge than formal training in inclusive teaching. Low self-efficacy in teaching skills was associated with negative attitudes in the current study, confirming previous studies, such as Sharma et al.(2012),Meijer(2015), and Savlianen et al.(2012). In future, it will be important to focus on teachers' knowledge—and particularly on enhancing pedagogical content knowledge related to disabled students—when aiming to positively influence teachers' attitudes towards inclusion. In addition, knowledge about specific disabilities and/or conditions has been reported to positively impact attitudes (de Boer et al., 2011). This indicates that overall strategies for inclusive teaching may not be sufficient and that pedagogical content knowledge may be enhanced by insight into specific diagnoses and how they can affect students and their learning.

Overall, the results of the present study indicate that teachers with knowledge, skills, and training in the area of special education in the UAE are significantly more positive than untrained teachers in their attitudes towards teaching disabled children in mainstream classrooms.

In conclusion, to promote better practice in the inclusion of students with disabilities, it is important to empower teachers and other teaching staff in the UAE to deal with difficulties in their schools. This may be achieved by enhancing their knowledge, qualifications, and positive experience in inclusive education in the area

of special education through counseling and training in the fields of integration, remedial education, and classroom management.

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